

Home Based Exercise Training To Improve Aerobic Capacity And Functional Limitations Of A Patient Following Pulmonary Embolism: A Case Report

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Received: 12th May. 2025

Revised: 08th Aug. 2025

Accepted: 12th Aug. 2025

ABSTRACT

Background: Aerobic training within rehabilitation setting has been effective in improving functional limitations following Pulmonary embolism (PE). Developing an effective exercise program along with monitoring progress becomes difficult with limited space and equipment in home-based setting. Furthermore, keeping patient motivated away from social distractions in home and compliance in following exercise program forms an integral part of care.

Objective: This case study describes in home physical therapy care of a patient post PE.

Materials and Methodology: This is a single case report study. The patient was selected on the basis of her presentation. A patient in her 70s had chief complains of shortness of breath with minimal exertion and limited ability to participate in activities of daily living. Aerobic training was provided for 12-weeks, twice a week with home exercise program established for remaining days of the week.

Results: Over 12 weeks, the patient showed significant improvements in aerobic capacity, exercise tolerance, and performance on daily tasks, as measured by various outcome measures, including the 6-minute walk test (6MWT), modified physical performance test (MPPT), shortness of breath questionnaire (SOBQ), and five times sit to stand test (FTSTS). The results support the clinical utility of individualized, home-based physical therapy programs for older adults post-PE, demonstrating substantial functional gains and symptom relief.

Conclusion: This case report highlights the effectiveness of a home-based rehabilitation program in improving cardiovascular fitness, functional capacity, and quality of life in an older adult recovering from pulmonary embolism (PE). Further research is required to determine its efficacy in preventing long term morbidity.

Keywords: pulmonary embolism, aerobic training, fatigue, 6MWT, SOBQ

INTRODUCTION

PE is the result of a thrombus most commonly originating from the deep veins of legs. People at risk are those who are inactive or bed-ridden, are receiving chemotherapy, have a history of blood-clotting disorders, overweight or obese, a smoker, had recent injury or trauma to a vein, are pregnant or taking oral contraceptives and above the age of 60.¹ It is a potentially life-threatening condition with 100,000 to 200,000 patients dying every year due to the condition.² It not only has a high mortality rate but for those who survive, it has a negative effect on health-related quality of life with long-term effects of causing pulmonary hypertension and severe activity limitations.^{3,4} PE is medically managed with thrombolytic therapy, anticoagulation with

unfractionated heparin and surgical embolectomy where the conservative treatment fails or is contra indicated. The ease of administration and drug management has enabled early discharge of patients from the hospital. Increasingly, patients with PE are referred to home-health care after the patient is stabilized in the hospital.⁵

In a randomized controlled trial of patients with persistent dyspnea following pulmonary embolism, those who participated in an eight-week, twice-weekly exercise-based rehabilitation program demonstrated greater improvements in exercise capacity and pulmonary embolism-specific quality of life compared to those who received usual care, with no adverse events reported.⁶ In another study of 23 anticoagulated patients following

acute pulmonary embolism, a 3-month exercise program was found to be safe with no exercise-related adverse events, and led to significant improvements in peak VO_2 ($p=0.05$) and quality of life at 6 months, including functional ($p=0.03$) and physical health ($p=0.03$) scores.⁷ In another study conducted in outpatient center among 27 patients who completed a 12-week personalized rehabilitation program, significant improvements were observed in training intensity, PE-specific quality of life, fatigue, and functional status, indicating that rehabilitation is a safe and effective intervention.⁸

Despite these promising findings, most existing rehabilitation models for PE remain clinic-based or hospital affiliated, with limited evidence supporting the feasibility, safety, or effectiveness of home-based rehabilitation. Effective and well monitored medical care at home can be cost-effective along with preventing hospital-acquired complications such as pressure sores, falls and trauma, delirium, malnutrition, pneumonia, and urinary tract infection. Furthermore, while cardiac and pulmonary rehabilitation programs are well established for conditions like myocardial infarction or COPD, similar structured programs are not yet widely implemented for PE survivors. This case report uniquely contributes to the current literature by illustrating a home-based rehabilitation protocol for a medically complex, older adult patient following acute PE. It highlights the feasibility of implementing a progressive exercise program within the home health setting, tailored to the individual's physiological needs. It also addresses a significant gap in current practice which is the lack of accessible, real-world rehabilitation model for PE patients discharged to home care.

OBJECTIVE

This case report details in home exercise training of a patient post PE in presence of a complex medical background to improve her aerobic capacity and cardiovascular endurance thereby improving her participation in activities of daily living (ADLs) and quality of life.

Case Description

A female patient in her 70s was hospitalized due to difficulty in breathing. She did not experience any pain but mentioned having “jittery” feeling in her legs. Multiple tests in the emergency department confirmed the diagnosis of PE. She was treated with parenteral anti-coagulants via catheters and was kept under observation for a few days after which she was discharged directly to home with a referral for home health services and rehabilitation care.

The patient was a good candidate for home-based rehabilitation as she was medically stable and discharged home after PE treatment, cognitively intact and able to follow instructions, functionally independent prior to hospitalization, living in a home environment suitable for mobility training, including stairs, free from acute cardiac or respiratory distress requiring hospitalization or supplemental oxygen. Additionally, the patient did not exhibit any cognitive impairments or unstable medical conditions.

Her medical history included right ventricular dysfunction, acute respiratory failure, asthma, anxiety, and GERD. She had been using CPAP at night for sleep apnea for the last few years. Her BMI was 28.2 Her past medical history included a family history of deep venous thrombosis.

Patient reported being physically active throughout her life except for the last few months due to death of a family member. Prior to hospitalization, she was independent in all activities of daily living and self-care, was driving and working part-time. She lived in a two-story house with her spouse and had to negotiate 14 stairs to reach to her bedroom on the second floor. Patient's daughter lived nearby and visited her frequently. Patient verbalized increased anxiety owing to her medical condition, difficulty, and fatigue in performing ADLs, shortness of breath in negotiating stairs and generalized weakness.

Patient reported having productive cough with clear sputum (frequently at night). She denied chest pain, palpitations at rest and use of supplemental oxygen. She reported taking over the counter cough suppressants for her allergies to pollen and dust.

Neuromuscular system revealed no loss of deep sensation with occasional numbness at night in right wrist. Gross muscle strength (3/5) was within functional limits (WFL) for both lower extremities. Generalized stiffness in the morning which improved with activity throughout the day. Integumentary, speech/hearing, and cognition was intact with no impairments.

Clinical Impression 1

Assessment of vital signs revealed blood pressure 132/86, pulse 86/min, respiratory rate 19 and oxygen saturation was 97%. Limited chest wall expansion observed during inspiration with no shortness of breath at rest. Peripheral edema was 2+ using the Digital Pressure Method. This subjective scale with grades 1+ to 4+ is generally used by healthcare professionals to grade pitting edema. The scaling depends on the depth of the “pit” or indentation and the duration it remains.

Patient’s comorbidities required careful consideration during examination and developing interventions. Patient’s decreased activity tolerance, prior level of function, motivation to participate in physical therapy, strong family support and good cognitive status deemed her an excellent candidate for physical therapy.

Examination

Patient was able to perform all functional transfers independently without the need of an assistive device and ambulated for 30 feet with standby assistance. Upon negotiating a flight of 14 stairs, she required 2 rest breaks in between and relied heavily on pulling the handrails through her upper extremities with step to pattern for completion of the activity. She reported her perceived exertion as 5/10 for the activity on the Borg scale. Post activity vital signs were blood pressure 162/88, pulse 114/minute and SpO₂ was 90%.

The six-minute walk test (6-MWT) has been utilized in a variety of cardiopulmonary conditions as a measure of exercise tolerance capacity⁹. A study done in community dwelling older adults concluded that the distance walked in 6 minutes moderately correlated with lower body strength ($r = 0.67$), standing balance ($r = 0.52$) and self-reported physical functioning ($r = 0.55$) with high test-retest

reliability (0.95) deeming it a valid and reliable test to assess functional status of older adults¹⁰. It was administered per American Thoracic Society guidelines in a flat, indoor hallway with a marked 30-meter course. The patient was instructed to walk as far as possible for 6 minutes, taking rest breaks as needed. Distance walked and need for rest were recorded. Pre- and post-test vitals, including pulse oximetry and rate of perceived exertion (RPE), were documented.

The patient walked a total distance of 210 meters in 6 minutes which is considered low according to the normative values for age and condition. She reported her perceived exertion as 6/10.

Participation in ADLs was assessed through Modified Physical Performance Test (MPPT). The test described by Reuben and Siu consisting of 9 functional items is highly reliable (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.87) with high inter-rater reliability (0.99)¹¹. It is administered using a 7-item version including tasks such as chair rise, walking 50 feet, and stair climbing. Each task is scored from 0 to 4, based on time and quality of performance. Patient scored 21/36 which put her in the category of “moderate frailty”.

Fall risk assessment was done through 5- times sit-to-stand test (FTSTS) which is a valid ($r = 0.64$) and reliable measure of dynamic balance in older adults¹². The patient was instructed to stand up and sit down five times as quickly as possible from a standard-height chair without using her arms. Time to complete the task was recorded using a stopwatch. Verbal encouragement was provided during the test. Score of 17.3 seconds put the patient at risk for falls.

The SOBQ was self-administered with supervision to ensure understanding. The patient rated her level of shortness of breath during a range of ADLs on a 6-point Likert scale. The total score was used to quantify the impact of dyspnea on daily life.

Patient completed the SOBQ with a score of 88/120. A higher score revealed increased fatigue and difficulty with activities of daily living.

Clinical Impression II

At the time of evaluation, she was diagnosed with acute respiratory failure and right

ventricular dysfunction and the reconditioning associated with it can be seen in the results of the tests performed.

The patient was found to have deficits in cardiovascular endurance, functional capacity, and standing balance with high risk for falls. Patient ambulated very limited distances inside the house and had difficulty walking on uneven terrains. Patient found it exerting to even climb the flight of 14 stairs to go to her bedroom. Though the gross lower extremity strength was found WFL, it was necessary to improve strength to improve balance and reduce the risk for falls.

Patient's physical therapy plan of care consisted of warm-up session with stretching exercises, strengthening- resistance exercises, interval training, and endurance training with a cool down period. Education regarding energy conservation techniques, deep breathing exercises, and relaxation exercises was also added to help with anxiety. Patient's main goals were to ambulate at least 200 feet inside and around the house, improve the ability to ascend and descend a flight of 14 stairs without getting fatigued and resume her work as soon as possible.

Intervention

A study done by Noack, et al¹³ concluded that exercise training is safe and effective in patients with embolism.

The patient was seen for physical therapy (PT) twice a week for 12 weeks. Each PT session lasted for approximately 45-60 minutes. A home exercise program was established to be followed on non-therapy days which mimicked a complete PT session.

Patient participated in stretching of upper and lower extremities before the beginning of each session to prepare the cardiovascular system for aerobic training. Patient's blood pressure, heart rate and oxygen saturation (SpO₂) were monitored before and after each exercise during the PT session by the therapist and by the patient on non-therapy days.

Exercise intensity can be prescribed using 50 to 85% of the maximum oxygen uptake (VO₂) achieved on a graded exercise test. Patient was instructed to exercise between the rating of 3 and 6 on the Borg scale as the rating of 3 corresponds to approximately 50% of VO₂ and 6 corresponds to 85% of VO₂. Patient was

instructed to avoid experiencing symptoms of excessive fatigue, breathlessness, muscle cramps or pain.

Strength training of upper and lower extremities was performed using ankle weights and TheraBand. Resistance training was based on the principle of one repetition maximum. She initiated with 1.5 lbs. ankle weights and level 2 TheraBand to perform a single exercise for 8-10 repetitions. As she progressed with performing 3 sets of 8-10 repetitions of an exercise with lower perceived exertion and fatigue, she was progressed to next level of resistance. Gait training was done initially on an even surface inside the house for up to 100 feet. As patient progressed, gait training was further challenged with longer distance and walking outdoors on an uneven surface for up to 250 feet.

Interval training consists of high-intensity bouts of exercise (30 seconds to 3 minutes) with brief rest periods or low-intensity exercise (30 seconds to 2 minutes). It engages the peripheral musculature through anaerobic metabolism so that exercises can be carried out with favourable cardiorespiratory responses. Patient participated in interval training during walking and strengthening exercises with a gradual decrease in duration and frequency of rest periods in between. The PT session ended with a cool-down period consisting of 5-10 minutes of low-level aerobic activities to bring the cardiovascular system to a steady state of rest.

The timeline for the interventions is as follows:

Weeks 1–2: Initial Conditioning

- Upper and lower extremity stretching to prepare for aerobic training
- Introduction to aerobic exercises at 50% VO₂ max (Borg RPE 3)
- Initiation of strength training with 1.5 lbs ankle weights and Level 2 TheraBand
- Gait training on even indoor surfaces up to 100 feet.

Weeks 3–6: Progressive Strengthening & Aerobic Training

- Incremental increases in resistance and repetitions based on the one-repetition maximum principle.

- Enhanced aerobic training targeting up to 85% VO₂ max (Borg RPE 6)
- Introduction of interval training: 30 seconds to 3 minutes of high-intensity bouts with brief rest periods
- Gait training extended to 250 feet, including outdoor uneven surfaces

Weeks 7–10: Functional Training & Endurance Training

- Further progression in resistance levels as tolerated
- Extended interval training durations with reduced rest periods
- Gait training incorporating obstacles and uneven surfaces.
- Dynamic balance and coordination exercises
- Preparation for resumption of daily activities, including driving and part-time work

Weeks 11–12: Outcome Assessment

- Final assessments to evaluate improvements in functional capacity
- Reinforcement of HEP.
- Patient confident to resume driving independently and part-time employment.

RESULTS

By the end of 6 weeks, the patient was able to ascend and descend up to seven stairs without a rest break and 14 stairs requiring a rest break using handrails. She was able to ambulate approximately 110 feet inside the house on a consistent basis. Vital signs were blood pressure 142/82, pulse 96/minute and SpO₂ was 95%. Perceived exertion was 3/10.

Table 1: Outcome Measures

Test	Pre-intervention	Post-intervention	Percent change
(6-minute walk test) 6MWT	210 meters	390 meters	85.7% (Improvement)
(Modified physical performance test) MPPT	21/36	31/36	47.6% (Improvement)
(Shortness of breath questionnaire) SOBQ	88/120	69/120	-21.6% (Improvement)
Five-Times sit to stand (FTSTS)	17.3	10.2 sec	-41.0% (Improvement)

After 10 weeks, patient was able to tolerate interval training combined with walking up to 200 feet and stair training exercises. Improved tolerance was based on the steady decrease in time required for “recovery” heart rate to come to rest and patient’s subjective assessment of performing a particular task with less exertion as scored on the Borg scale. Throughout the remaining course of treatment, she showed consistent progress with all exercises and following home exercise program well. At the end of 12 weeks, she felt confident enough to resume driving and her part-time job.

The 6MWT distance increased by 180 meters, representing an 85.7% improvement, well above the minimal clinically important difference (MCID) of approximately 30–50 meters in cardiorespiratory populations, indicating a substantial gain in functional capacity. The MPPT score improved from 21 to 31 out of 36, a 47.6% increase, reflecting enhanced physical performance in daily tasks. The SOBQ score decreased from 88 to 69, marking a 21.6% reduction in perceived dyspnea, which exceeds the MCID of approximately 5–8 points, suggesting a meaningful decrease in symptomatic burden during ADLs. The FTSTS time improved from 17.3 to 10.2 seconds, a 41.0% decrease, surpassing the MCID of 2.3 seconds used in older adult populations, indicating better lower extremity strength and functional mobility. Collectively, these results demonstrate both statistically and clinically significant improvements following the home-based rehabilitation intervention.

It can be concluded that in-home exercise program was beneficial in improving cardiovascular fitness and functional capacity of the patient.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this case report was to document the outcomes of physical therapy management for an older adult presenting with reduced aerobic capacity and functional impairments following an episode of PE. Over the course of 12 weeks, the patient demonstrated substantial improvements in aerobic capacity, exercise tolerance, endurance, and performance in ADLs.

Objective improvements were observed across all outcome measures. These outcomes are in line with findings from previous research. Parker et al.¹⁴ reported significant improvements in dyspnea and disease-specific quality of life in a rehabilitation group, as measured by the SOBQ. Additionally, the structure of this patient's home-based program bi-weekly sessions over 12 weeks parallels the protocols used in other studies that demonstrated improvements in muscle strength, mobility, and patient-reported well-being¹⁵. Importantly, the patient not only met her physical therapy goals but also reported subjective benefits, stating that she felt "stronger and healthier" at discharge.

This case highlights the feasibility and clinical utility of implementing structured, home-based rehabilitation programs for older adults recovering from PE. It supports the growing body of evidence that individualized physical therapy can lead to meaningful functional gains, symptom relief, and restored independence. Broader implementation of similar programs may improve outcomes for patients unable to access outpatient rehabilitation.

CONCLUSION

Currently, the literature supports the early initiation of exercise training after an episode of thromboembolism^{13,14}. In this case report, the positive results could be attributed to the patient's high functioning prior level of function, strong family support and adherence to following home exercise program well. Combining several functional tests (6MWT, MPPT, SOBQ) captures the patient's progress comprehensively. Such methods could be adopted in clinical practice, allowing for more complex assessment approaches to enhance outcomes. Limitations with exercise tolerance,

generalized deconditioning, decreased activity level and lower quality of life are seen in patients approximately 1 year post PE¹⁶. Also, post PE syndrome classically characterized by ventricular dysfunction, decreased functional capacity and quality of life is common in patients after an episode of PE¹⁷. Hence, further research is required to determine the efficacy of in-home physical therapy in preventing long-term morbidity related to PE.

Lack of a comprehensive CVP assessment was a limitation of this study. Little research has been done regarding the benefits of in-home physical therapy in patients with cardiovascular and pulmonary disorders. Given the promising results of this single case, larger-scale studies are needed to evaluate the generalizability and scalability of home-based PE rehabilitation. Future research should include multicentred randomized controlled trials comparing home-based versus outpatient rehabilitation, ideally with diverse patient populations including older adults, those with multiple comorbidities, and patients in rural or resource-limited settings. Investigations into the appropriate frequency, duration, and intensity of home-based programs as well as the role of telehealth or remote monitoring will be essential in establishing comprehensive guidelines for post-PE rehabilitation across settings.

Ethics Approval

This case report was reviewed under the MedStar Health Research Institute (MHRI) guidelines and was determined not to constitute human subject's research. According to the August 1, 2017 memo from the MHRI Office of Research Integrity, case reports involving fewer than three patients do not meet the Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS) or Food and Drug Administration (FDA) definitions of research and are therefore exempt from Institutional Review Board (IRB) review and approval.

The report was prepared in compliance with HIPAA guidelines. No identifiable patient information is included, and IRB exemption applies per MedStar policy.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This author has no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to sincerely thank Rameez Mirza for his continued support, encouragement, and understanding throughout the development of this case report.

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